

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL INNOVATION IN A TERRITORIAL PROCESS (CASE STUDY ALBANIA)

Aldona Minga,

Doctor of Philosophy

Fan S Noli University of KORCA

Ilir Sosoli,

Doctor of Philosophy

Fan S Noli University of KORCA

Dorjan Marku

Doctor of Philosophy

Fan S Noli University of KORCA

Abstract

We will discuss what social innovation is, how it can be used in the territorial context in Albania and the impact it has on the development of communities and regions. In Albania, social innovation has influenced the development of the territory by bringing new and creative solutions to social challenges. Some examples of social innovation include social startups, incubators and innovation hubs, projects in the field of tourism and cultural heritage, as well as projects for the improvement of the environment and the protection of nature. These efforts have aimed to address social problems and promote the sustainable development of the territory. However, there is still room for further growth and development of social innovation in Albania, and cooperation between the public sector, non-governmental organizations and the private sector is important to create a supportive environment for social innovation.

Keywords: Social innovation, territory, factor, development, economy.

Concept of Social Innovation

The early concept of innovation in economic development and entrepreneurship was popularized by Joseph Schumpeter, a German economist. Innovation, according to him, includes the elements of creativity, research and development, new processes, new products or services, and advances in technology (Lumpkin & Dess, 2001). According to (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2004), innovation is the creation of new wealth or the change and enhancement of existing resources to create new wealth.

Innovation is also seen as a process of idea generation, a development of an invention and ultimately the introduction of a new product, process or service to the market (Thornhill, 2006). Social Innovation is the process of developing and implementing creative and innovative solutions to address social challenges and improve the economic, social and environmental condition of a community.

The concept of social innovation represents a vision that includes the creation and development of new solutions to create value and improve social life and the social environment. This strategy uses innovation to meet social challenges, using a combination of creativity and new ways of thinking to bring about major and lasting changes in society.

Social innovation is closely related to transforming situations and creating innovative solutions to complex social challenges. These may include issues such as poverty, lack of education, limitations in access to health and social services, and environmental pollution, to name a few. In contrast to the use of traditional methods, social innovation aims to develop new, creative solutions oriented towards positive change in society.

Many writers and personalities have made significant contributions to the field of social innovation, including academics, activists and numerous professionals in social fields. One of the leading texts in this field is "The Power of Social Innovation" by S. Goldsmith (2010), which underlines that social innovation is a great power that enables us to develop new solutions to the biggest social challenges of our time. Instead of just using the old methods, we need to go beyond them and build a more just and different reality. The emergence of social actors' initiatives to satisfy specific social needs and offer solutions to different problems derives mostly from the employment crisis and the reshaping of State interventions (Bouchard, 2011). In this context, social innovation plays a central role in solving new societal problems.

Success situations of social innovation include examples such as changes in the education system, the use of technology to address health problems, the creation of social business models and many others. These innovative solutions offer hope to address major social challenges and improve people's lives in ways that are sustainable and different from traditional methods.

Westley, F., & Antadze, N. (2010) explored a strategy for scaling social innovation and increasing its impact. He discusses the importance of collaboration, experimentation and adaptive learning in the process of scaling social innovations.

Nicholls, A., Simon, J., & Gabriel, M. (2015) provided an overview of new frontiers in social innovation research. Mulgan, G. (2006) explores the process of social innovation and identifies the stages and key elements involved. It discusses the role of actors, networks and context in driving social innovation processes. In

the book Murray, R., Caulier-Grice, J., & Mulgan, G. (2010) provided a comprehensive overview of social innovation, including case studies and examples from different sectors and countries. It covers topics such as citizen-led innovation, social finance and public sector innovation.

In Albania, social innovation is an important tool to improve territorial processes and to achieve sustainable goals at the local and regional level.

Social Innovation in Territorial Processes

The role of territory is crucial in the context of social innovation and its impact on development. Territory, which refers to a specific geographical area, plays an important role in shaping the conditions and dynamics of social innovation processes.

1. **Contextual factors:** The territory offers a unique context that affects the emergence, implementation and diffusion of social innovation. Factors such as the socio-cultural environment, economic conditions, political structures and physical infrastructure shape the possibilities and constraints for social innovation initiatives.

2. **Cooperation and the formation of networks:** in a territory they serve as a basis for close cooperation and the creation of connections between different actors, including individuals, organizations, communities and institutions. Collaboration between different sectors and stakeholders within a territory has the potential to advance collective efforts and increase the effectiveness of interventions in the field of social innovation.

3. **Local knowledge and assets** are valuable resources for territories, providing specific knowledge, skills, resources and cultural heritage that can be harnessed to build social innovation. These local knowledge and assets not only contribute to the identification of relevant social needs, but also serve to co-create innovative solutions and ensure that interventions are relevant and sustainable by being rooted in the local context.

4. Social innovation usually focuses on **solving local challenges** and improving the quality of life for communities within a particular territory. Place-based solutions consider the unique features and needs of a particular geographic area. The aim is to create positive impacts in social, economic and environmental aspects, adapting to the specific context of that country.

5. The territory serves as an environment for the **development of policies and governance structures** that encourage and promote social innovation. Local and regional authorities play a key role in creating an enabling environment, providing resources and establishing supportive policies and regulations that facilitate social innovation processes.

In general, the territory is not just a background for social innovation, but an active actor that helps shape and adapt social innovation initiatives. The factors that determine the greater innovativeness of one area compared to another, are, in fact, much more complex. To the concept of physical proximity, we must add cultural proximity, that is a sense of belonging to an area, capacity for interaction with others, and shared

common values, which, in short, determine relational capital (Dedeire & Minga 2021). And it is precisely relational capital, consisting of various forms. Recognizing the role of territory enables a deeper understanding of contextual factors, collaborations and local dynamics that have an impact on the outcomes and sustainability of social innovation in a given geographic area. Recent researchers have identified a link between innovation and territorial change in the way businesses are organized, supply chains, and international networks emerge in response to new technologies and relationships between major manufacturing firms, suppliers, and buyers (Gereffi & Korzeniowicz, 1994). "A successful territorial innovation system can create the needed basis for cooperation among companies and specialization, improve the private-public dialog, encourage external stakeholders (suppliers, buyers, etc.) and accelerate innovation. Regional and territorial development are essential for improvement of the socio-economic conditions of the entire country (Kozak & Muca 2020)

The Impact of Social Innovation on Territorial Processes in Albania.

Social innovation in Albania has had a significant impact on the transformation of the territory through the development of innovative projects and the undertaking of positive changes at the local and regional level. This type of innovation has played a key role in improving the quality of life for Albanian citizens, addressing social, economic and environmental challenges in a creative and innovative way.

One of the key dimensions of the impact of social innovation on territorial development is the connection between different actors, including local government, non-governmental organizations, the private sector and local communities. These actors collaborate to identify social challenges and develop innovative solutions that respond to the specific needs of local communities.

In the context of Albania, social innovation has been focused on many important sectors. One of the focuses has been improving public services, including education, health, infrastructure and transport. Through social innovation, projects and initiatives have been developed to improve citizens' access to these services and to address their needs in a more effective and innovative way.

Also, social innovation has influenced the field of local economic development in Albania. Through the creation of innovative projects in the sectors of tourism, agriculture, handicrafts, and information and communication technology, the creation of new jobs and the increase of the economic income of local communities have been stimulated.

In addition to the economic aspect, social innovation has an important impact on the social and cultural aspect of the territory. Through innovative community involvement projects, connections between individuals and different groups have been strengthened, promoting cooperation, solidarity and cultural diversity.

The impact of social innovation on territorial development in Albania requires strong institutional and financial support. It is important for the country's situation, that the government and appropriate institutions

create specific policies and programs to stimulate social innovation and provide financial resources for the development of innovative projects. Public-private partnerships serve as a key element to mobilize various resources and create a supportive environment for social innovation in Albania.

Social innovation has a significant impact on territorial processes in Albania, through innovative projects, cooperation between different actors, and institutional and financial support, social innovation contributes to the improvement of the territory in social, economic and cultural aspects. In the future, it is important to continue efforts to promote and strengthen social innovation in Albania, creating a supportive and encouraging environment for the development of the territory in a sustainable and inclusive manner.

The importance of institutional and financial support

Institutional and financial support is of great importance for social innovation, not only at the global level, but also in the context of Albania. If I take it in the general context, institutional support provides the structure and legislation necessary to improve the environment in which social innovations operate. Public institutions, such as local and central governments, can create specific policies, laws and programs to promote and finance social innovation. Also, financial support is necessary to facilitate the development and growth of social innovation. Funds and financial resources, such as grants, investments and public-private partnerships, can be catalysts for the growth of innovative initiatives and for their expansion to achieve the greatest impact.

In the context of Albania, institutional support is necessary to improve the climate of social innovation. Government and public institutions should create dedicated policies and programs to promote social innovation, identify social challenges and facilitate the creation of partnerships with non-governmental organizations and the private sector.

However, the challenge of financial support continues to be stable in Albania. Beyond some local and international initiatives to provide funding and financial resources for social innovation, there is a need for greater investment in this direction. Public and private funds, as well as other funding sources, have the potential to help increase social innovation and create a supportive environment for territorial development in Albania.

Institutional and financial support provides opportunities for the creation and development of social innovations in a certain territory such as Albania. This support creates a more favorable environment for social innovations and contributes to improving the development of the territory, including solving social challenges, increasing economic income and promoting environmental sustainability.

In fulfilling the potentials of social innovation in the territorial processes in Albania, a stable institutional and financial support is necessary. Some key aspects are:

- Public and private investment: Financial interventions from government and private investors have

an important role in helping social innovation expand its impact. Public investments in infrastructure, social services and local development can create new opportunities for social innovation. At the same time, private investors can support innovative projects with the potential to bring about positive change in communities. It is very important to understand that innovation is essential for the improvement and development of businesses, generating more profits, as a result, this will lead to the development of the territory where it operates. (Jano, K. & Minga, A 2023)

- Public-private partnerships: Cooperation between the public and private sectors is essential for the promotion of social innovation in Albania. For example, strategic partnerships between local government and local business can encourage the development of social innovation projects in the territory.

A successful system of territorial innovation can create the necessary basis for cooperation between companies and specialization, improve private-public dialogue, encourage external stakeholders (suppliers, buyers, etc.) and accelerate innovation. Due to proximity, both geographically and in activities, the members of the spatial innovation system enjoy several benefits and economic advantages. (MINGA, A., & MUÇA, E. (2023). The absence of the economic structures in the process of collection and distribution of the products has encouraged the development of the direct circuits of commercialization, from rural producers to intermediaries, or from agro-enterprises to regional intermediaries. (Muca E, et al 2018)

- Technical assistance and training: Providing technical assistance and training to local actors is another important aspect to promote social innovation. Training in areas such as project management, social finance, new technologies and community leaders help increase capacities to develop and implement social innovation in territorial processes.

Conclusion

Social innovation has a great impact on territorial processes in Albania. Using creativity, technology and collaboration, social innovation can improve access to basic services such as education, health, infrastructure, and influence the economic and social development of an area. However, to achieve success in using social innovation in territorial processes, it is important to understand the local and cultural context and adapt to it. Going down this path, it is necessary to involve local actors and link cooperation between them, including the government, non-governmental organizations and the community.

In this way, social innovation can serve as an effective tool to solve territorial challenges in Albania and improve the livelihood of local communities.

a. Improving dialogue and participation: Social innovation encourages the active participation of all local actors in territorial processes. Using new tools and technologies, it is possible to create virtual platforms, online surveys, mobile applications and other tools to encourage dialogue and citizen participation in the decision-making process.

b. Development of sustainable business models: Social innovation can contribute to the development of

sustainable business models at the local level. Through the implementation of social innovations, new opportunities can be created for local businesses, which can be based on the use of resources available in the territory, the trade of traditional products and the use of technology to increase efficiency and competitiveness.

c. The use of technology and innovation to solve the challenges of the territory: In Albania, social innovation can be used to address the specific challenges of a territory, such as public transport, water management, renewable energy infrastructure, etc. Using technology and social innovation, new solutions can be developed and the quality of life in the territory can be improved.

References

1. G.T Lumpkin, Gregory G Dess. Linking two dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation to firm performance: The moderating role of environment and industry life cycle, *Journal of Business Venturing*, Volume 16, Issue 5, 2001, Pages 429-451, ISSN 0883-9026, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(00\)00048-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(00)00048-3)
2. Nasser Fegh-hi Farahmand. Organizational Business Development of Hospital by Laboratory Services. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*. 2013; 1(6):119-127. doi: 10.12691/jbms-1-6-1.
3. Thornhill, S. Knowledge, Innovation and Firm Performance in High-and Low-Technology Regimes. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 2006. 21, 687-703. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2005.06.001>
4. Goldsmith, S. The power of social innovation: How civic entrepreneurs ignite community networks for good. Jossey-Bass, 2010, 304. doi:10.1177/0899764010381625
5. BOUCHARD, M.J. "Social innovation, an analytical grid for understanding the social economy: the example of the Québec housing sector", *Service Business*, 2011, 6(1), 47-59
6. Westley, F., & Antadze, N. Making a Difference Strategies for Scaling Social Innovation for Greater Impact. *The Innovation Journal: The Public Sector Innovation Journal*, 2010, 15(2), 1-19.
7. Gereffi, G. and Korzeniewicz, M., Eds., *Commodity Clains and Global Capitalism*, Praeger, Westport, 1994, 95-122.
8. Nicholls, A., Simon, J., Gabriel, M. Introduction: Dimensions of Social Innovation. In: Nicholls, A., Simon, J., Gabriel, M. (eds) *New Frontiers in Social Innovation Research*. Palgrave Macmillan, London. 2015. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137506801_1
9. Geoff Mulgan, *The Process of Social Innovation*, *Innovations: Technology, Governance, Globalization*, 2006, 1, (2), 145-162.
10. Murray, R., Caulier-Grice, J., & Mulgan, G. Social innovator series: Ways to design, develop and grow social innovation. *The open book of social innovation*. Nesta / Innovating Public Services, 2010.
11. Minga, A., et al. Local development through social and territorial innovation: A case study of Puka Region. *European Academic Research*. – Vol. X. – Issue 10. – January, 2023.
12. Jana, K., Minga, A., Muaremi, L The Role of the Business in the Development of the Territory *European Academic Research*. – Vol. XI. – Issue 1. April 2023
13. Muca, E., Kapaj, A., Thoma, L. EXPORT OPPORTUNITY AND CONSTRAINTS FOR FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PRODUCERS IN ALBANIA. *Annals of Marketing Management and Economics*, 2018, 4 (1), 65-71. <https://doi.org/10.22630/AMME.2018.4.1.5>
14. KozakS., & Muça E. Is membership of the European Union a sufficient factor to improve the level of regional development? The case of Albania and voivodeships in Poland. *Scientific Journals of the Małopolska University of Economics in Tarnów*, 2020 46(2), 13-27. <https://doi.org/10.25944/znmwse.2020.02.1327>